

ATTITUDE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS OF MURSHIDABAD TOWARDS STUDIES

Dr. Bhupendra Narayan Basunia

Assistant Professor

Altab Hossain Primary Teachers Training Institute

Murshidabad, WB

Abstract:

We very commonly hear that he or she suffers from attitudinal problem. His attitude towards studies is not good and consequently is not performing well. She is not able to mix up well with the neighborhood due to her typical attitude. All these are indicative that the word attitude is a household word for most of us. We however need to delve through this article the attitude of secondary school children towards studies and how does it affect their performance in general and academic performance in particular. The study was carried out based on the sample survey of six schools in and around Murshidabad through projective technique by administering questionnaire to 100 students belonging to six secondary schools with a view to assess the attitude towards studies of secondary school students both component wise and in totality, and ascertain attitudinal difference among secondary school students with respect to gender, management, medium of instruction, place of habitation, etc. Results of the study inter-alia indicated that girl students of private schools of urban location have the higher mean score thereby showing positive attitude towards studies as compared to the students of government schools of rural areas with vernacular as medium of instruction. This might have been due to the fact that the student of urban

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location, have a flair for education and they are in search of high-profile job. Girls of this area are also comparatively advanced and they have surpassed and shown superiority over boys in all walks of life.

Key Words: Attitude, Attitude towards studies, Medium of Instruction

Introduction:

"Once you start building a more positive attitude, life will throw some incredible opportunities your way!" - Jeff Keller

Attitudes are important components of personality structures that determine the character of an individual. Attitude is both an affective and cognitive concept. Affectively, an attitude includes values and sentiments. These affective elements of an attitude reflect themselves in the emotional reactions of an individual in his day-to-day behavior. Cognitively, attitudes represent the perceptions of subjects and objects, events and activities, as the person eventually comes to perceive them in life. As such, an attitude may be defined as the psycho-conceptual state of mind towards men, matter, or material, a thought, action or life as a whole.

Attitudes are judgments. They develop on the "ABC" model (affect, behavior, and cognition). The "affective" response is an emotional response that expresses an individual's degree of preference for an entity. The "behavioral" intention is a verbal indication or typical behavioral tendency of an individual. The "cognitive" response is a cognitive evaluation of the entity that constitutes an individual's beliefs about the object. Most attitudes are the result of either direct experience or observational learning from the environment. Unlike personality psychology, attitudes are expected to change as a function of experience.

Attitudes determine attachment-detachment, affinity-aversion, identification-indifference and likings-disliking of an individual for the subjects-objects of his daily life. Attitude symbolizes one's potential will-power, zeal and zest to do or not to do one thing or the other. It is the

placement-value of the person to engage or disengage himself in an activity. It is because of his attitude towards something that an individual comes to own or disown it. Virtually, attitude exercise itself as the vital emotional force with which an individual occupies himself at any line of thought or place of action. In its practical implications, attitudes are generally positive or negative views of a person, place, thing or event-- often referred to as the attitude object. People can also be conflicted or ambivalent toward an object, which means they simultaneously possess both positive and negative attitudes toward any issue or the item in question.

Attitude towards Studies:

Attitude is a hypothetical construct that represents an individual's degree of like or dislike for anything. Attitudes are made, modeled and modified by the experiences, observations, impressions and perceptions of an individual in his life. Students' attitude towards studies manifests their mental make up for the studies. Do they really love to pursue studies or they do not actually like to be at studies, is a fundamental question of their attitude towards studies. Attitude towards school studies can be considered in terms of two basic and fundamentally different attitude dimensions. The first is the like – dislike dimension or the affective dimension; and the second is the importance – unimportance or perceived value dimensions. Students attitude towards studies may be perceived to be in-built in their feelings for studies, their perception of utility of studies to them besides including their attitude towards schools, books, home task and teachers as such. According to a study conducted by DANI (1984) about 80 per cent of the students had positive attitude, which showed decreasing trend with increase in age and the rural students had low level of scientific attitude as compared to urban students. BHARDWAJ (1985) conducted a study to determine the role of attitude as a process in the shaping of psycho-dynamic contents of personality in terms of needs, perception, anxiety, conflicts defense mechanism and functions of ego and super ego. BABU (2004) conducted a study to determine the higher secondary students' attitude towards the study of commerce and their adjustment and found out that boys' attitude towards the study of commerce was better than the girls. Similarly, the rural students, private school students and

English medium students' attitude towards commerce were better as compared to urban students, government managed schools' students and Tamil medium students. SANCHEZ; ZIMMERMAN (2004) conducted research to study the secondary students' attitudes towards mathematics.

Attitude can change:

Educationists accept and respect the unique personality of each and every child. Through proper and befitting education, the child is facilitated to attain all-round development of the person in him. In teaching-learning situations, studies serve as means for the achievement of the ends of education. Truly, in an ultimate analysis, education means studies and studies mean education.

Jeff Keller in his book 'Attitude is Everything' has highlighted the fact that attitude is very important for achieving coveted goal. According to him, it is the attitude which determine success or failure in any activity we pursue and therefore he says attitude is everything. Tesser (1993) has argued that hereditary variables may affect attitudes but believes that they may do so indirectly. For example, if one inherits the disposition to become an extrovert, this may affect one's attitude to certain styles of music. There are numerous theories of attitude formation and attitude change. These include Consistency theories, which imply that we must be consistent in our beliefs and values. The most famous example of such a theory is cognitive dissonance (Dissonance-reduction) theory, associated with Leon Festinger, although there are others, such as the balance theory of Fritz Heider, Self-perception theory associated with Dary Bem, Persuasion Elaboration Likelihood Model associated with Richard E. Petty and the Heuristic Systematic Model of Shelly Chaiken, etc.

Attitudes can be changed through persuasion. The celebrated work of Carl Hovland, at Yale University in the 1950s and 1960s, helped to advance knowledge of persuasion. In Hovland's view, we should understand attitude change as a response to communication. Anderson (1983) suggests that the inter-structural composition of an associative network can be altered by the activation of a single node. Thus, by activating an affective or emotion node, attitude change may be possible, though affective and cognitive components tend to be intertwined. In primarily affective networks,

it is more difficult to produce cognitive counterarguments in the resistance to persuasion and attitude change (Eagly & Chaiken, 1995). Affective forecasting, otherwise known as intuition or the prediction of emotion, also impacts attitude change. Research suggests that predicting emotions is an important component of decision making, in addition to the cognitive processes (Loewenstein, 2007). How we feel about an outcome may override purely cognitive rationales.

In terms of research methodology, the challenge for researchers is measuring emotion and subsequent impacts on attitude. Since we cannot see into the brain, various models and measurement tools have been constructed to obtain emotion and attitude information. Measures may include the use of physiological cues like facial expressions, vocal changes, and other body rate measures (Breckler & Wiggins, 1992). For instance, fear is associated with raised eyebrows, increased heart rate and increase body tension (Dillard, 1994). Other methods include concept or network mapping, and using primes or word cues (Shavelson & Stanton, 1975).

Some research on emotion and attitude change focuses on the way people process messages. Many dual process models are used to explain the affective (emotion) and cognitive processing and interpretations of messages. These include the elaboration likelihood model, the heuristic-systematic model, and the extended parallel process model. In the Elaboration Likelihood Model, or ELM, (Petty and Cacioppo, 1986), cognitive processing is the central route and affective/emotion processing is often associated with the peripheral route. The central route pertains to an elaborate cognitive processing of information while the peripheral route relies on cues or feelings. The ELM suggests that true attitude change only happens through the central processing route that incorporates both cognitive and affective components as opposed to the more heuristics-based peripheral route. This suggests that motivation through emotion alone will not result in an attitude change. In the Heuristic-Systematic Model, or HSM, (Chaiken, Liberman, & Eagly, 1989) information is either processed in a high-involvement and high-effort systematic way, or information is processed through shortcuts known as heuristics. Emotions, feelings and gut-feeling reactions are often used as shortcuts. The Extended Parallel Process Model, or EPPM, includes both thinking and feeling in conjunction with threat and fear appeals (Witte, 1992). EPPM

suggests that persuasive fear appeals work best when people have high involvement and high efficacy. In other words, fear appeals are most effective when an individual cares about the issue or situation, and that individual possesses and perceives that they possess the agency to deal with that issue or situation.

Objectives of the study:

The study has been designed with the following objectives:

1. to assess the attitude towards studies of secondary school students both component wise and totality.
2. to study attitudinal difference among secondary school students with respect to sex, management, medium of instruction, place of habitation.

Hypotheses of the study:

To realize the objectives stated for the study, the following hypotheses have been formulated in null form, as they are more akin for testing:

1. There exist no significant differences in the attitude of the students towards studies in relation to sex variation.
2. There exist no significant differences in the attitude of the students towards studies in relation to management variation.
3. There exist no significant differences in the attitude of the students towards studies in relation to the medium of instruction.
4. There exist no significant in the attitude of the students towards studies in relation to the place of habitation.
5. Secondary school students do not possess a favorable attitude towards studies.

Methodology:

The Method:

The normative survey design of descriptive method was undertaken to study the problem.

The Sample:

The sample for the study was drawn from the secondary classes of six different schools of Murshidabad. All the students of class X of these schools were considered as sample. These six schools were selected randomly from among the total schools considering the type of management, location, medium of instruction and school type. Out of six schools, two schools from each of the variations were selected. Then the total students reading in these six schools were categorized under urban or rural, government or private, English medium or Hindi medium and boy and girls.

Analysis and Interpretation:

The result of the present study showed that girls students of private schools, urban location school students and students from English medium school have the higher mean score compared to the total sample, thereby showing positive attitude towards studies. But student of government schools, rural schools and Hindi medium schools along with the boys sub- sample have not indicated positive attitude towards studies. This might have been due to the fact that the student of urban location, have a flair for education and they are in search of high profile job. Girls of this area are also comparatively advanced and they have surpassed and shown superiority over boys in all walks of life. The private schools are highly paid in terms of fees and still were in high demand by the parents may be because these schools have their own educational environment. The results of the sample are presented below:

Total mean score values on all the intra variables and total sample on

Attitude towards studies:

Variation	Sub Samples	Total Attitude Scores	
		Mean	SD
Sex	Boys	236.43	19.05
	Girls	251.12	13.29
Management	Govt. School	242.79	18.18
	Private School	246.48	18.31
Place of habitation	Urban	244.69	18.10
	Rural	242.72	18.52
Medium of Instruction	English	244.69	18.10
	Hindi	242.72	18.52
Total		244.23	17.11

Findings of the study:

The findings based on the results obtained through projective technique can be summarized given below:

1. There was significant difference in the attitude of secondary school students towards studies in relation to sex variation. It was found that female students have projected positive attitude towards studies in comparison with the male students.
2. It was observed that the private schools' students scored much higher mean value in all components than the government school students indicating that private school students possess a positive attitude towards studies as compared to the government school students.
3. Similarly, students from urban area scored much higher mean value in all components than the students from rural areas indicating positive attitude towards studies than the students from rural area.

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4. Likewise, the students from English medium school scored much higher mean value in all components than the students from Hindi medium school displaying positive attitude towards studies than the students from Hindi medium schools.

Recommendations:

The development of active personality is the goal of education. Proper perception of the significance is the vital to enhance the prestige of education, as well as to raise the intellectual and spiritual level within society. We develop our attitudes and over time we form habits, of which we usually have little awareness. Not all our habits are helpful and some can be destructive or goal defeating. But, since our attitudes are learned, they can be unlearned. Many negative attitudes stem from ignorance. This means we can often change our attitude with the right knowledge. Education is a well-defined process for the development of desirable attitudes in the personality profile of children. The success in this direction much depends upon the success of education in the development of desirable attitude of children towards their studies. For all practical purposes, students' attitude towards studies must be a positive or healthy one. It is the yard stick of their very much required intrinsic motivation for studies. As a result of this research study and from the literature survey the following recommendations are made:

- (i) **Inculcate and enhance positive attitude through sensitization:** All-out effort must be made towards inculcating and enhancing positive attitude towards studies at primary and elementary level to instill positive outlook among children and their sensitization towards the importance of education so as to provide firm base for better acquisition of knowledge.
- (ii) **Family must assume greater responsibility:** A child is the product of the family. The quality of a family contributes significantly in development of positive attitudes in a child. The family members therefore have to be conscious of their obligation to develop positive attitudes in child. This will not only help the child to excel in his chosen field of studies but will also pave the way towards making a positive society and thereby a academic achievement conscious student fraternity.

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- (iii) **Transformation of attitude by school:** The school is equally responsible for developing good and positive attitudes in students not only towards studies but in different walks of life, prominent amongst them could be love and respect for the motherland, cultural and social integration to promote and preserve unity in diversity, protection of environment and sustainable development, disaster management, respect towards parents, aged and elderly people, etc. The emphasis therefore has to be accorded towards transformation of negative attitudes into a positive one through better curriculum, debate and discussions, exhibition, study tours, student exchange programs, science fair, excursion, etc.
- (iv) **Need based course curriculum:** The curriculum should be flexible and should be tailored in such a way to address the present-day needs of the students without over burdening them. At elementary level, the syllabus must be reduced and fixed portion should be allotted in order to improve knowledge, perception, abilities, skills and attitude towards studies. While attempting to review and reduce, we however should not lose sight of global change in education arena and the all-round development. The course should therefore be in tandem with the international standard duly following the best practices.
- (v) **Promote self study concept:** One strong theory of student responsibility for learning is called “self-regulation”. Studies have suggested that self-regulating learners show more ability to control their thoughts, feelings, and actions in support of learning; self-directed learners know how to deal with frustration and keep themselves on task in the face of difficulty (Corno, 1993); self regulated learners have both the “will” and “skill” to learn (Pintrich & DeGroot, 1990), and their problem-solving behaviours are similar to those of experts (Schoenfeld, 1989). The more students take responsibility for their own learning, the more likely they are to attribute success to their own efforts, which in turn is likely to increase levels of effort and persistence (Hagen & Weinstein, 1995; Pintirch, 1994).
- (vi) **Adopt Problem-based learning (PBL):** PBL is a pedagogical strategy that organizes learning around a driving question and provides students with opportunities to design problem-solving, decision making, and investigative activities, which often results in products or presentations

(Thomas, 2000). When students are strongly motivated (as is often the case when they use technology in math), they are likely to be more willing to take on deeper mathematical challenges. Effort needs to be initiated to adopt problem-based learning especially in case of mathematics.

Conclusion:

Murshidabad is already doing well in education and in fact is ahead of many districts and has won many accolades in recent years. The State Government is actively participating in all spheres of educational development through higher budgetary allocations, improved pay scale to teachers, capacity building programs, improvised infrastructure, e-learning, etc. We now need to concentrate on transformation of attitude of the student community and inculcate among them the sense of competitiveness, burning desire to excel in studies, especially to the children belonging from rural background. This is an achievable goal given the higher outreach of education, unstinted support from the government, literacy ratio above the national average, higher teacher-student ratio, etc. A concerted effort by guardians, school community and the students themselves through attitude transformation will surely bear fruit and will help to harness the latent talent of students.

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